

Enhancing archaeological research with “holograms”. Mixed Reality implementations in field- and laboratory work

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ABSTRACT

Mixed Reality (MR) is a technology that blends digital elements with the real world, offering immersive tools not only to visualize but also to document and interpret archaeological data. Thus far, it has been increasingly implemented in museums and heritage sites so as to boost visitor engagement, while applications in archaeological research remain limited. This study aims to address this gap by exploring the potential of MR as part of an archaeologist’s toolset for documenting and interpreting archaeological data both in situ and in a laboratory setting. Two case-studies have been chosen. In regards to the first one, the Documenting And Triaging Cultural Heritage (DATCH) software is used for on-site documentation of architectural features. For the second case-study a prototype animal reference collection for wild species is developed, designed to complement conventional zooarchaeological reference material. The central research questions concern how MR can support documentation, visualization, and contextual analysis of archaeological features, and to what extent these tools can be integrated into excavation and laboratory workflows. In examining these questions, this study evaluates MR’s capacity to enhance spatial understanding, promote interactive and collaborative engagement with archaeological data and provide supplementary resources for teaching.

Keywords: Mixed Reality, archaeological fieldwork, reference collections, documentation

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Introduction

36 As it can be seen on the following diagram (Figure 1) Mixed Reality (MR) is located in the
 37 middle of the so-called Virtuality Continuum, which has the real world on the one side and a
 38 completely virtual world on the other (Milgram & Kishino, 1994, pp. 2-4). Combing aspects of both
 39 Augmented Reality (AR) and Augmented Virtuality (AV), MR can be described as an environment
 40 that blends digital elements with the real world (Fogliaroni, 2018, p. 13).
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43 **Figure 1** – The Virtuality Continuum as described by Milgram and Kishino (1994)

44 MR and AR applications in Archaeology have been around for more than 2 decades by now.
 45 The majority of these projects aimed at enhancing the experience of visitors in archaeological sites
 46 and museums. Bridging the two realities provides the opportunity to learn about a specific site or
 47 artefact in a more intuitive way, which can be highly beneficial from a knowledge acquisition
 48 perspective (Bekele et al., 2018, pp. 16-17). Visitors are motivated to actively participate through
 49 these tools, contributing to the rise of the concept of edutainment, or educational entertainment
 50 (Innocente et al., 2023, p. 274).

51 As far as applications in archaeological research are concerned, however, they consist only a
 52 small fraction of the applications of Immersive technologies in the Cultural Heritage and
 53 Archaeology sectors (Bekele et al., 2018, pp. 21-22; Dilena and Soressi, 2020, p. 2). It is this small
 54 section that will be the point of emphasis of this paper. The work presented below is the end
 55 product of my Master's thesis at Leiden University. I am also following Liang's (2021, pp. 250-251)
 56 definitions regarding MR and AR.

57 More specifically the aim is to explore the potential and limitations of MR as part of an
 58 archaeologist's toolset for recording and documenting, both at the trowel's edge and in a laboratory
 59 setting. In order to achieve this two distinct case-studies will be presented, each concerned with
 60 different aspects of archaeological research.

61 In regards to fieldwork, such applications have started developing since the start of the 2000s
 62 and have advanced significantly since, providing immersive tools for data visualization and
 63 enabling new perspectives for archaeological interpretation. From the beginning the aim was the
 64 creation of a virtual environment where the user would be able to examine different types of
 65 archaeological data, from stratigraphical units to the location of specific finds after they had been
 66 excavated (Benko et al., 2004, pp. 1-2; Kayalar et al., 2008, p. 5). Advancements in hardware have
 67 highlighted the potential of MR technology during fieldwork, although much work remains in order
 68 for it to become a standard tool when conducting fieldwork. More recently, for example, 3D models
 69 of previously removed structures can be anchored to their original location (Figure 2), opening new
 70 ways for analyzing excavation data (Cobb & Azizbekyan, 2024, p. 378).
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Figure 2 – The 3D model of an unearthened wall, placed on its original location after it had been removed. The MR device used in this case is Meta Quest Pro (Cobb & Azizbekyan, 2024, p. 378, Figure 14).

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The main question in this case-study relates to how can MR be used in the documentation, visualization and contextual analysis of different archaeological features, unearthened during fieldwork or still-standing in a site? Furthermore, to what extent can such tools be implemented in the workflow of an archaeological excavation?

As far as the second case study is concerned, the aim was to examine how can MR support the documentation of artefacts. It specifically addresses a zooarchaeological problem, related to digital reference collections for animal bones. As far as physical reference collections are concerned, they are used for multiple reasons, serving research but also teaching purposes. The creation of reference collections in digital environments has been one of the main points where computational methods have been applied to zooarchaeology (Spyrou et al., 2022, pp. 2-3).

There have not been many similar applications in a MR environment thus far. Virtual reference collections are not a novelty in research, in most cases, however, these are web-based platforms. The Bonify project consists an interesting case-study, where both a web-based platform and an XR environment are created and evaluated by researchers and students (Nobles et al., 2019, p. 5708). More specifically, the team behind the Bonify project experimented with a Smartphone-based AR device that uses cards as markers in order to toggle the 3D models of the animal bones in question (Figure 3). The evaluation of the platform indicates that such virtual environments can solve issues related with accessing physical reference collections. In some cases, political and/or logistical reasons can hinder access to laboratories equipped with zooarchaeological reference material (Nobles et al., 2019, p. 5706; Spyrou et al., 2022, p. 3). The portability of the platform was another reason why users indicated they would be willing to use similar ones in the future.

126 A key functionality of the software is the “Draw” tool (Figure 4), which enables users to create
127 straight lines, curves, or more complex shapes through a simple pinching gesture with the thumb
128 and index finger, effectively simulating the use of a digital pen. By activating the “Close Shape”
129 option, these lines can automatically connect to form polygonal or irregular shapes. The tool also
130 allows customization of line color and thickness, facilitating clear differentiation between recorded
131 features.
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134 **Figure 4** – The menu of the DATCH software, toggled by facing the palm of your
135 hand. The “Draw” function can be seen on the bottom left of the menu.

136 Additionally, the “Create” tool provides options for adding measurements and annotating
137 features in multiple ways. Tags can be inserted and anchored at points of interest, offering a
138 practical means of identification and documentation. Measurement capabilities are supported by
139 the “Measuring Tools”, which include the “Measuring Tape” for recording two-dimensional
140 attributes, such as height and width, and the “Measuring Cube”, for three-dimensional analysis.
141 Spatial organization in mixed reality can be achieved through the “Peg Grid”, which generates a
142 customizable grid with adjustable dimensions and peg spacing. This feature streamlines the
143 establishment of excavation grids, such as those used for trench layout, and allows individual pegs
144 to be manipulated, including color changes, to mark subdivisions within an area—for instance,
145 during micro-excavations. For smaller contexts, the “Drawing Plane” could be also useful. More
146 specifically, it is a two-dimensional grid, where lines can be anchored to intersections to ensure
147 precise measurements of features.

148 **Case-study #2: Development of a MR Reference Collection**

149 The following workflow outlines the development and configuration of the prototype Virtual
150 Animal Reference Collection for the HoloLens 2, detailing the software environment, asset
151 preparation, and interaction design. All steps are presented in the flowchart below as well (Figure
152 5).
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Figure 5 – Workflow for the creation of the Virtual Animal Reference Collection using MRTK in Unity 3D.

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This platform was developed in Unity using the Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK) (Microsoft, n.d.-a). This Unity project was configured for the Universal Windows Platform, the standard for HoloLens applications. The MRTK, together with the OpenXR Plugin, was imported via the Mixed Reality Feature Tool. These packages provide pre-built interaction systems (hand gestures, gaze) and user interface components (menus, buttons), reducing the need for custom coding. The MRTK XR Rig was added to manage camera tracking and hologram interaction, while the Input Simulator allowed testing of movements and interactions without the headset.

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A 3D model of a juvenile hippopotamus skull was obtained from Sketchfab, a platform containing many high-quality 3D models, serving educational and public science purposes. More specifically, it is [the skull of a juvenile hippopotamus](#) (*Hippopotamus amphibius*) from the collection of the Lapworth Museum in Birmingham (specimen TN015A). The model was downloaded in .glb format and optimized with the Windows MR Asset Converter (Microsoft, n.d.-b) to reduce polygon count and ensure smooth performance on the HoloLens 2. Within Unity, it was imported as a GameObject (the standard container for all visible and interactive items in Unity) and assigned a GLTF Asset component to ensure correct rendering. Interaction was enabled by combining a Box Collider (defining its physical boundaries), an Object Manipulator (enabling movement, scaling, and rotation), and a Constraint Manager (restricting interactions to realistic parameters, e.g., limiting rotation to the horizontal axis and preventing downscaling below real-world size). Scaling up was permitted, however, to allow closer inspection of details.

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To support interpretation, metadata (species, age, sex, anatomical unit, and data about its creator) was added using TextMeshPro and linked to the model so that it moved together with it. A script, connected to a pre-built MRTK button, allowed toggling the text on and off to avoid clutter during object-focused observation.

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Finally, a custom Measuring Tool was created. Two movable Unity cubes served as anchor points, connected by a line that updated dynamically to display the distance between them. This measurement, shown as on-screen text aligned with the user's viewpoint, allowed both real and virtual objects to be assessed within the MR environment.

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At this stage the MR environment applied in each case-study has been presented. In the next section, the outcomes of both case-studies will be discussed, focusing on their practical functionality, their limitations and their potential integration in an archaeologist's everyday toolkit.

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Results and Insights

188 Case-study #1: Documenting during fieldwork with the DATCH software

189 Overall, the DATCH software proved relatively intuitive, with smooth transitions between
190 functions. However, interaction responsiveness was sometimes inconsistent, with occasional
191 delays in button activation and instability in gesture recognition.

192 The “Draw” feature enabled detailed tracing of masonry contours, though automatic shape
193 closure introduced inaccuracies such as protrusions and gaps (Figure 6).

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195 **Figure 6** – Drawing of a portion of the masonry of the Bailelekas tower. A) On-site
196 view of the drawn features. B) The same portion of the wall toggled in an indoor
197 setting, after fieldwork.

198 These issues were especially evident when drawing adjacent stones or curved edges, where
199 the algorithm occasionally misconnected nodes (see Figure 6A). Despite these limitations, the
200 overall geometry of stones was successfully recorded. The portions of the wall digitized were also
201 toggled in an indoor setting after fieldwork was completed. Opening the DATCH file after fieldwork
202 poses the challenge that the user cannot choose the exact location where the features will appear,
203 which could limit interaction with the data (see Figure 6B).

204 As far as the “Measuring Tape” function is concerned, it allowed clear and accurate length and
205 width measurements, both for individual stones and larger architectural features, such as the
206 western side of the north medieval tower of Mytikas. Nonetheless, the placement of multiple tapes
207 could be cumbersome, as there is the danger of moving the wrong one by accident (Figure 7).

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209 **Figure 7** – Making measurements in DATCH. View of a portion of the western side
210 of the northern Mytikas tower. A) On-site view. B) The same portion toggled in an
211 indoor setting.

212 Tags were added to features that could be of special interest, such as spolia on the masonry,
213 or postholes. It should be mentioned that the input could be much lengthier (Figure 8).

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215 **Figure 8** – Adding tags to features, in order to mark them and interpret them. In this
216 case, a posthole on the masonry is marked.

217 Field testing under varied lighting confirmed that all features functioned outdoors, although
218 working under direct sunlight severely limited the visibility of the virtual drawings. Despite initial
219 concerns, the headset's weight and transparent display did not significantly hinder movement
220 across uneven terrain. As a next step it is important to enable exporting DATCH files in different
221 formats, ensuring data reuse.

222 Documenting with DATCH presents many similarities with the interface for digital drawing
223 implemented in Çatalhöyük (Forte, 2014, pp. 14-16). In that case, the aim was the creation of a
224 digital record of excavated units and finds as well as possible interpretations and ideas (Figure 9).
225 There is one important difference however. DATCH provides an embodied experience, which can
226 enhance our perception of the surrounding space as users are motivated to move around an
227 environment filled with visual and sensorial stimuli. This sense of embodiment can lead towards
228 more critical interpretations of a site, as Opitz and Johnson stress (2016, pp. 5-6). Given access
229 to many researchers this could play the role of a supplementary excavation diary, where ideas and
230 theories are collaboratively explored.

231 Furthermore, DATCH can promote spatial thinking as it highlights the relationship between
232 different features, both on- and offsite. Recent applications both from the field of Virtual Reality
233 (VR) (Lercari et al., 2018, p. 378) and MR (Cobb & Azizbekyan, 2024, pp. 378-379) have
234 highlighted the importance of interpreting 3D features anchored in their original location even after
235 their removal. This process allows researchers to make connections between features far more
236 easily, surpassing the limitations of 2D media.

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Figure 9 – The digital drawing interface implemented in Çatalhöyük (Forte, 2014, p. 16, Fig. 18).

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Case-study #2: The Virtual Animal Reference Collection Prototype

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The prototype Virtual Animal Reference Collection, after being accessed via the HoloLens 2 home menu, displayed the 3D model of a juvenile hippopotamus skull with the accompanying metadata (Figure 10). Testing took place in Leiden University’s Laboratory of Archaeozoological Studies, both by Dr. Laura Llorente-Rodriguez and me, where the model was evaluated alongside physical specimens from the Laboratory’s collection to assess usability, accuracy, and potential improvements.

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248 **Figure 10** – View of the 3D model of the *Hippopotamus amphibius* after toggling the
249 Virtual Animal Reference Collection on the HoloLens 2.

250 Interaction with the model was generally smooth and responsive, both at close range and from
251 afar, via hand rays. The ability to enlarge the specimen enabled detailed examination. Occasional
252 issues were noted, including the model unintentionally shifting position when interactions remained
253 toggled, which could be confusing for inexperienced users. A brief tutorial on HoloLens interactions
254 could mitigate this.

255 The metadata text followed the model as intended, though visibility was sometimes obstructed
256 by the physical environment (Figure 11). The toggle button functioned, but responsiveness was
257 inconsistent. The current version of this prototype does not support voice commands which is also
258 limiting in terms of accessibility.

259
260 **Figure 11** – View of the relevant metadata about the specimen used.

261 Comparison with physical specimens, particularly adult male hippopotamus bones,
262 demonstrated the value of the digital model for highlighting anatomical differences (Figure 12).
263 However, proximity to physical bones sometimes triggered unintended hand gestures, causing
264 accidental movement of the virtual specimen. Careful handling reduced this issue.

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266 **Figure 12** – Comparison of the 3D model of the juvenile *Hippopotamus amphibius*
267 with an adult specimen from the physical reference collection of Leiden University's
268 Laboratory of Archaeozoological Studies.

269 Last but not least, the custom measuring tool was functional and clear, though precision
270 required steady movement to avoid displacing the model when placing the cubes near it (Figure
271 13).

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273 **Figure 13** – The custom-made measuring tool. A) The virtual measuring tape is
274 placed on top of the model so as to measure its length. B) The value measured is
275 presented on the left of the model.

276 When compared with other initiatives such as the Bonify project (Nobles et al., 2019), this
277 prototype addresses several usability issues of the smartphone-based AR device used, particularly
278 by eliminating the need for external markers. As with all XR applications, motion sickness remains
279 a potential limitation (Nobles et al., 2019, pp. 5710–5711), yet the interface proved easier to use
280 and more stable. It should be stressed again that this prototype is not intended to replace physical

281 animal reference collections but to supplement them, especially for underrepresented species or
282 in remote settings where access to reference material is limited.

283 Beyond identification, the virtual reference collection has considerable educational potential.
284 Previous research demonstrates that immersive 3D models can enhance engagement and
285 learning outcomes (Di Franco et al., 2015; Bozia, 2023). By allowing users to manipulate and
286 examine specimens in space, the MR interface fosters embodiment and active learning, even if
287 tactile affordances are absent.

288 Future development could create a portable, cloud-based reference library accessible through
289 a MR headset, overcoming the logistical challenges of transporting archaeological material. In this
290 sense, the prototype has the potential to become a valuable addition to the zooarchaeologist's
291 toolkit, both in the field and during teaching.

292 **Conclusion**

293 Both case studies demonstrate the potential of MR for archaeological research, offering new
294 ways to document and interpret archaeological data. The DATCH software shows how MR can
295 enhance in-field documentation by combining 3D visualization with embodied interaction,
296 supporting both recording and hypothesis testing. While safety concerns, motion sickness, and
297 technical limitations remain, its integration alongside traditional methods could transform
298 collaborative excavation practices and post-excavation analysis.

299 The Virtual Animal Reference Collection prototype highlights MR's value in zooarchaeology by
300 supplementing conventional reference collections, especially for rare species. Moreover, its value
301 as a teaching tool should also be explored further. Though still limited in scope and in need of
302 broader testing, it demonstrates the feasibility of portable, accessible reference collections.

303 Overall, MR is not a replacement for established practices but a versatile supplement to them,
304 with applications across archaeological subfields. The key challenge lies in moving beyond novelty
305 to ensure practical, accessible, and user-friendly solutions that can be widely adopted in research.
306

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313

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